

ROLE OF LIBRARY IN CONFLICT AND PEACE PROCESS IN BAKASSI AREA OF NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

The Bakassi Peninsula has been a disputed piece of territory between Nigeria and Cameroon for decades and the source of several crises. Now, there is a volatile atmosphere in the area characterized by protests, agitation, communal conflicts, economic recession, high levels of unemployment, and hardship. Despite government efforts to reach peace agreement with the people, the levels of crisis have remained high. This paper explores alternative approach to managing crisis that will result in peace in Bakassi through proper information dissemination. Using the example of Bakassi community library and information center (BACLIC), this paper demonstrates that there some innovative ways that libraries can resolve conflict and improve the quality of life of any community. This is 2009 used questionnaire, in-depth interviews, direct observations, Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) and study of diary of activities/ functions/ events maintained by the staff of the center. Data were from one thousand and seventeen (1017) respondents. Findings reveal that libraries and information centers have very significant roles to play when social conflicts arise. Conflicts are based on deficiency of information. Access to high quality information is therefore of great importance to a society like Nigeria. The study proffers several recommendations which, if implemented, would reduce significantly conflict levels in Nigerian communities.

Keywords: Library, Conflict

INTRODUCTION

Bakassi, a peninsular in Cross River State, the South-South zone of Nigeria, has been a disputed piece of territory between Nigeria and Cameroon for decades and the source of several conflicts. The International Court of Justice decided on October 10, 2002 that the Peninsula should be under the sovereignty of the Cameroons and Nigeria agreed to turn over the peninsula. The handover process began in August 2006 when Nigeria made the formal handover of the northern part of the peninsula to the Cameroon and was completed in 2008. Bakassi indigenes and inhabitants were resettled in new Bakassi, Nigeria. The Nigerian government had designated the three Ikang towns - areas of Akpabuyo Local Government area - as the relocation and resettlement site for the Bakassi indigenes. The new Bakassi area continues to be faced with the challenge of establishing peace and development in the area. Numerous peace initiatives have been launched and vast amount of resources have been

utilized to craft peace agreements which have collapsed under the weight of competing interests. Attempts have, however, been made at the Federal level of Nigerian government to resettle the Bakassi people. On August, 2006, the federal government of Nigeria gave out one billion Naira for the resettlement of the Bakassi Peninsula indigenes. More recently, in 2008, Governor Liyel Imoke of Cross River State opened the six-kilometer road network and a 100-unit housing estate in New Bakassi. Unfortunately these attempts to reduce crisis in new Bakassi by the Nigerian government seems not to be very effective, as levels of conflict, violence and crisis are still quite high in the area. It was necessary to examine whether there other peace building strategies that could be adopted to complement existing efforts to promote peace in Bakassi.

Preliminary observations and informal discussions with some members of the community reveal that lack of adequate or balanced information could be significant cause of most of conflict and crisis in the area.

Information is a prerequisite to advancing democracy, participating in decision-making, developing the economy and enhancing the quality of life. Access to information cannot be achieved without involving libraries because they "are one of the building blocks of the local information and knowledge infrastructure" (Tise 2000). Furthermore, libraries embody a principle of rights of access to information and the acquisition of knowledge. Of all the institutions in democratic societies, only the library keeps itself above all morals, politics and religions. There was a need to conduct research to find out if the Community Information Centre is the sort of development vehicle needed to resolve conflict in the area. This study therefore was conducted to fill this knowledge gap by providing answers to these questions: what are the roles that BACLIC is playing in resolving conflict in Bakassi area of Nigeria? What are the incidences of conflict since the establishment of the centre?

LITERATURE REVIEW

Conflict is not a new phenomenon but rather it is a problem that has grown with time (VAN DER STOEL 1996). The writer, Shutte (1993) commented on conflict and stated that conflict can never cease to exist. Today, conflict poses a multi-dimensional challenge and is the most widespread problem in Africa. Conflict is part of the human nature. Obahchi (2008) advances the view that forging of relationships and attempts to continuously perfect them will always precipitate conflict.

Studies have been carried out on the role of libraries in conflict resolution. In the course of the elections in December 2007, Kenya experienced one of its biggest crises since independence. Conflict resolution became a crucial topic among the Kenyan society. The Goethe-Institute, Nairobi in conjunction with Kenya Library Association (KLA) chose conflict resolution as the theme of the annual conference of KLA organized in June 2008. The findings indicated that libraries are very significant institutions, when social conflicts arise (Obachi, 2008). Maheswaran (2008) in a study of roles of libraries in conflict and peace process in Sri Lanka reported that although conflicts are threats to libraries, they can play an important role in creating ethnic harmony. Libraries are expected to change attitude of the civil society, which is a stakeholder in the peace process.

Ifidon & Ahiauzu (2005&2006) studied on information and conflict prevention in Niger delta region of Nigeria and communication as instruments of conflict resolution, inclusion of role of community libraries in conflict resolution were mentioned. Exhaustive search of

the literature showed that no known study to the research has been conducted on any existing community library/ information center to determine its role in conflict resolution.

Bakassi Community Library and Information center (BACLIC)

Bakassi Community Library and Information Center (BACLIC), using the Bakassi town hall was incorporated on 14 January 2008 as a response to the enduring problem of conflict in new Bakassi area of Nigeria. BACLIC evolved out of the Bakassi Forum, which began in October 2007. BACLIC aims to focus attention on the many problems that threaten to perpetuate the crisis and conflict which have engulfed the new Bakassi area in recent times. Some of these problems are lack of good quality education, social problems like drug abuse and teenage pregnancy with their attendant risks of HIV/AIDS among young people, youth unemployment, , as well as an appreciable level of social misunderstanding among some of the wards. BACLIC is a non profit center established by individuals concerned with the social and economic situation of new Bakassi.

The center 's patron, include committed community developer, local business leaders, traditional leaders, and representatives from local authorities, academics, representatives from professional bodies, non- governmental, community-based organizations, concerned Bakassi citizens from across the wards that are willing to commit their time and resources to help call attention to some of the problems identified.

Activities of the center include convening meetings to sensitize members to the new idea of accessing information in the community center. Other activities include repackaging of information in local language -- through academic inquiry, practical engagement, and professional development for the community. BACLIC serves as a focal point for community members across the area and takes responsibility for the promotion of access to information. It provides community members with readings, social and professional networking connections. The center also takes interns on short-term contracts and offers professional exposure on how to repackage information. BACLIC also trains the Bakassi youths as information corps and upon completion of their training, trainees typically work to distribute information to community members.

BACLIC is being financed throughout by voluntary donations of patrons. Day-to-day expenses, mainly covering stationery, communication and refreshments, are borne by the coordinator and the chief executive of the center. A Bakassi citizen living in Virginia, USA, who is one of center's patrons, donated reading materials.

The center is run by volunteers, including the coordinator who is acting as executive secretary.. From time to time, other members contribute towards printing costs and help in kind. To ensure the sustainability of the foundation, a small endowment fund was set up in February, 2008, which came from donations received at the conference of stakeholders of education in Bakassi. Added to this local government grants are solicited. Normally, people are skeptical about accountability in Nigeria, the coordinator pastes the account on the center's notice board which will help enhance credibility for would-be philanthropists. Indeed, BACLIC, right from its infant stages, continues to have a strong representative support base to discharge its responsibilities and ensure its survival

Research Methods

This survey used five main methods to collect data: a questionnaire, in-depth interviews, direct observations, Focus Group Discussions (FGDs) and study of diary record of activities/

functions/ events maintained by the staff of the center. The use of combined methods is because the roles of a library are dependent upon the cultural and social factors within the community. Similar methods were used in other studies of roles of library in conflict resolution in Kenya ((Obachi, 2008).), in the Sri Lanka (Maheswaran, 2008).

Interviews

The researchers explained in detail, the study objectives and the possible benefits of the study. Also the clients were informed that the researchers have come to learn from them and will not take much of their time. The researchers could speak the local language and are more at home with ideas, views of life and practices in this area. This made the fieldwork much easier as they could understand the meaning of local terms. Also the coordinator, his subordinates, his personal secretary/assistant and other staff of the center were interviewed. The advantages of the interview is that it allowed the researcher to come in direct and personal contact with the client in a dialogue.

Study of Diary of Activities/ Functions

The researchers got some information from records of work. This provided a more reliable indication of roles the center has perform since inception.

Focus Group Discussions (FGDs)

The researchers had discussions with small groups. Members of the group were encouraged to mention in some detail the present work they are engaged in, the problems they face, the information required and the library role likely to be of interest and help in their work, including comments on how the existing roles should be tuned/ refined to suit their particular information needs. Moreover, through these discussions the changes that are taking place and that are likely to take place in future, could be ascertained and the center situation could be monitored. This would help in continuous modification and updating of the center to suit the changing needs.

Questionnaire

The questionnaire used in this study had seven items and was pre-tested. The first part of the questionnaire requested from respondents such personal information as age, gender, educational qualification. The second part elicited data on the role of BACLIC to reduce conflict, incidences of conflict since the establishment of center. The questionnaire was handed out to everyone entering the BACLIC for one week. The researcher assumed that everyone entering the center was a regular user. The questionnaire had accompanying text explaining the rationale for the survey. This study was undertaken during February, 2009.

Out of the one thousand two hundred (1200) copies of questionnaire distributed, one thousand and seventeen (84.75%) were returned with valid response. 183(15.25%) were not returned at all. Table 1 shows the distribution of respondents by age, gender and educational qualification.

Table 1: Background Information of Respondents

Age (Years)	NO	%	Gender	NO	%	Educational level	NO	%
17- 27	215	21.14	Male	877	86.23	Primary	274	26.94
28-37	608	59.78	Female	140	13.77	secondary	709	69.72
38 & above	194	19.08				Tertiary	34	3.34
Total	1017							

Source: Field Data (2009)

Findings

Respondents were asked to list the roles of BACLIC that they feel have helped to reduce conflict in new Bakassi area. The results revealed that 966 (94.98%) respondents listed news service, 921 (90.56%) listed forum; while 807 (79.35%) listed provision of services for job seekers. (Table 4)

Table 2 shows the respondents estimation of roles that BACLIC performs that help reduce conflict and crisis in new Bakassi

Roles	Frequency	%
Provide information about state and local business opportunities	765	75.22
Provide information about the community	597	50.70
	477	46.90
Provides information literacy skills	986	96.95
Helps students with their school assignments and schoolwork	536	52.70
Provide education resources and databases for adult/continuing education student	638	62.73
Provide information or databases regarding investments	716	70.40
Helps business owners understand and use technology, information resources,	253	24.48
	51	5.02
Helps patrons complete job applications		
Provide services for job seekers	807	79.35
Helps users access and use government services and resources	78	7.67
Telecommunications	103	10.13
Staff provide as-needed assistance to patrons for understanding how to access and use government programs, and services	34	3.34
Staff provide assistance to patrons applying for or accessing government services	549	53.98
BACLIC is partnering with government agencies, non-profit organizations, and others to provide services	479	47.10
Forums to enable all participate in decision-making	921	90.56
News service. .	966	94.98
circulates tape recordings of radio news and national events in the local language	765	75.22
a reading room for newspapers, a .	392	38.54

Help them to acquire the skills, knowledge and confidence to participate fully in community affairs.	286	28.12
Provide computer and Internet skills training	361	35.49
offers technology training to those who would otherwise not have any	298	29.30
Exhibitions, Display of information or posters,	902	88.69

Note.—does not total to 100%, as respondents could select more than one option
Source: Field Data (2009)

Incidences of conflict since the establishment of BACLIC in new Bakassi

This information was obtained from diary of activities of the center and from government publications. The records show that there is a decline of conflicts and crisis since the establishment of the center in 2008 (Table 3).

Table 3 shows the incidences of conflict since relocation to new Bakassi

Year	Frequency	%
2006	13	27.08
2007	28	58.33
2008	6	12.5
2009	1	2.09
Total	48	100

Discussion

The respondents indicated that news service is one of the most popular products of the center.

During the interview, the coordinators and staff of BACLIC revealed that the center circulates tape recordings of radio news and national events in the local language. It was noted that in the majority of the cases the issue of currency of the news never arises. These rural dwellers seem to be content with having access to “any” news. In addition to playing audiotapes with local news, some staff of the center has also started taping news from the radio for the benefit of the community. This approach help all (literate, neo-literate and even illiterate) to obtain information to raise their educational standards, advance democracy, participate in decision-making, develop the economy and enhance the quality of life. This finding is similar to the investigations of Ngulube (2000), using the example of one rural library in the Mudzi District in the north-eastern part of Zimbabwe, that news service was rated very highly by the rural population, Similarly, studies by Abid, (1995) in meeting. The information needs of rural communities reported that news service was significant. Exhibitions and displays is the next role indicated by most respondents

To meet some of the community’s information needs the center mounts exhibitions from time to time. The frequency of updating the information depends on its currency and popularity with users. Complemented are displays which are both in English and Efik, the local language. It is interesting to note that no cases of vandalism have been reported by the centre. The coordinator updates the displays when new information. According to the coordinator, the ultimate objective is to offer custom-tailored products that suit the needs of the community. During the FGDs a respondent stated “the center exhibitions have helped calm Bakassi because we are aware of plans. Adimorah (1996) similarly found exhibitions are necessary in community information provision Similar results were obtained by Alemna (1995), who reported that exhibitions is accepted in community libraries.

Forums are listed by respondents as role that has reduced conflict. The coordinator indicated that forums are held on holidays (Christmas and Easter days) to ensure that most people will be at home. These enable the center to get first hand information on the crisis and gave the Bakassi people the opportunity to express their needs. The forums help Bakassi people to acquire knowledge and confidence to participate fully in community affairs which will enhance the quality of life. Similar findings were obtained by Ngulube (2000), that forums are necessary in rural libraries. He stated that existence of a library is dependent upon the cultural and social factors within the community. Collection development policies in the developing world should take into consideration all appropriate media because books are often rare and inappropriate for the majority of the people.

During the FDGs one of group members stated that the activities of center have increased the community's awareness of the role of the library. People from nearby areas are now visiting the more that they used to when it was established People come seeking information in various formats. Notwithstanding copyright implications, the coordinator indicated that they have recorded some published works on cassettes to cater for the various needs of the community. Translation of materials into the local languages is being actively pursued. These rural dwellers can now count the number of people who have been employed through the information obtained from the centre. Community has now internalized the library as their major source of information.

The incidences of conflict have reduced significantly since the establishment of the centre. Well-informed communities are able to exercise their democratic rights, as well as playing an active role in society. Freedom, prosperity and the development of society and of individuals are closely related to access to information. Libraries are a prerequisite to raising educational standards, advancing democracy, participating in decision-making, developing the economy and enhancing the quality of life. In other words, information empowers and improves human beings and reduces conflict.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

There are many lessons that can be drawn from the case study. Findings reveal that libraries and information centers have very significant roles to play, when social conflicts arise. Conflicts are based on deficiency of information and history characterized by conflict could also be recorded as a history of disinformation Access to high quality information is therefore of great importance of a society like Nigeria, Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations that will result in control of increasing levels of conflict in the community are suggested:

A robust and innovative library is an essential factor to resolve conflict and improve the quality of life of any community.

Libraries should use the limited resources at their disposal to ensure every community has access to information

There is need to repackage information so that it benefits a wide spectrum of the community

- Libraries should stretch their boundaries and make themselves relevant to the communities they are serving.

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